

NEWSLETTER

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Intermediate/Surrogate Endpoints Balancing Speed and Scientific Rigor

We hope you managed to have a relaxing summer break. It is hard to believe that the new academic year has started. Many from the working group team were able to meet in person at JSM in Portland. We hope that we can meet in person at a future conference, perhaps the upcoming ASA biopharmaceutical workshop in Maryland.

This newsletter is themed on endpoint surrogacy in oncology drug development. In April, the ODAC voted unanimously 12:0 in favor of MRD as an endpoint suitable for accelerated approval in multiple myeloma. This newsletter includes a thoughtful reflection on the meeting, contributed by Gu. This ODAC meeting sparked hot discussions in the community about what comes next. In addition to regulatory considerations supporting accelerated approval, a critical topic for sponsors in oncology drug development is determining the optimal strategies for making Go/No-Go decisions ensuring that resources are allocated effectively. As Mullard wrote in Nature Reviews Drug Discovery in 2023 "... around \$60 billion per year is spent on unsuccessful cancer drugs ... More work is needed on the predictive validity of R&D tools". Over the past decades, several intermediate and surrogate endpoints have been identified to evaluate the effectiveness of cancer drugs, including objective response rate (ORR), pathologic complete response (pCR), minimal residual disease (MRD), circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA), progression-free survival (PFS), and tumor growth (g). A significant body of research has been devoted to understanding the relationship between these endpoints and long-term survival benefits, aiming to establish their validity as predictors of overall outcomes. However, given the complexity of various disease settings, continued research efforts remain essential to further elucidate these relationships and optimize their use in drug development and clinical practice.

Gormley classified the oncology endpoints into 4 categories: clinical benefit endpoints, surrogate endpoints that predict clinical benefit, surrogate endpoints that are reasonably likely to predict clinical benefit, and intermediate endpoints. Ananthakrishnan et al. provides more detailed information in the Biostat Bytes section. Chen et al. compiles the existing data to understand the role of pCR across various solid tumors. We hope you enjoy reading the KOL message by Devlin who was greatly involved in the research of the MRD endpoint.

In addition, this newsletter also includes the recent FDA approvals from OCE, ODAC meetings and some updates. We hope that this newsletter is informative for benefiting our efforts to develop innovative and effective drugs for cancer patients.

Dr. Phillip He and Dr. Laura Fernandes
Co-chairs

Dr. Philip He

Dr. Laura Fernandes

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KOL Message

My Journey with the MRD ODAC

By Sean Devlin †

The recent Oncologic Drug Advisory Committee (ODAC) meeting in April 2024 [1] was a milestone in my career in biostatistics. It culminated years of research I had done alongside Dr. Ola Landgren as part of the EVIDENCE team investigating minimal residual disease (MRD) as an early marker of clinical benefit for patients with multiple myeloma. It was not until the end of 2023 that I found out there would be an ODAC meeting to review the use of MRD as an early marker for myeloma. At that point, I also learned that we would jointly present data with i2TEAMM. While I knew there was an independent group conducting a similar analysis, I knew very little about i2TEAMM—I wondered what randomized studies they included, how they constructed the MRD endpoint, and what were the results of their analysis?

"With the potential use of MRD for accelerated approval in myeloma now, the horizon has broadened for other malignancies that incorporate similar disease-monitoring assays...."

With ODAC planned for April 2024, both teams quickly arranged collaborative meetings to review all the analyses. With the impending scrutiny of ODAC, I knew that Dr. Shi and I would need to develop a thorough understanding of each other's analytic approach. Only half of the randomized studies ended up being shared across the two projects when examining MRD at a sensitivity of 10^{-5} in the newly diagnosed setting, and there were also some differences in how the primary MRD endpoint was calculated across the two teams.

After meeting with Dr. Shi, the two independent analyses coalesced nearly perfectly. She was the perfect partner statistician—rigorous, transparent, and amicable. Dr. Shi previously worked on various analyses of surrogate endpoints, and those experiences gave her a wealth of knowledge.

After vetting the approach and results of the two teams, it was clear that, despite some numerical differences, the two analyses were consistent and complementary. Both teams then agreed on a strategy for the ODAC meeting, the ordering of presentations, and who should respond to which questions if they arise. That left everything in place except for one last critical component: the exact positioning of the FDA and its independent meta-analysis results, something I was unaware of until shortly before the ODAC meeting.

I cannot do justice to the FDA's presentation in this short correspondence. For any statistician interested in developing early endpoints that could be used for accelerated approval, I strongly recommend watching the video and reviewing the slides provided on the ODAC website. The presentation covered the accelerated approval pathway, mitigating the risk of early approval, overall survival as a safety endpoint, and potential trial designs. Key information was also provided during the question-and-answer portion of the meeting when ODAC members asked the FDA about the requirements for intermediate endpoints. To my surprise, the FDA received far more questions from ODAC members than the EVIDENCE or i2TEAMM members.

So, what's next for multiple myeloma? As drug development continues, more randomized trials will systematically incorporate high-quality MRD testing into their protocols. With these additional data, the next goal may be attainable: evaluating whether MRD can be considered a validated surrogate for regulatory approval in myeloma. While I am optimistic, it will take years before these trials have readouts for the survival endpoints.

With the potential use of MRD for accelerated approval in myeloma now, the horizon has broadened for other malignancies that incorporate similar disease-monitoring assays. We have gained knowledge from this experience with the FDA and April's ODAC. Now we just need the data.

†About the author: For the past 13 years, I have worked as a faculty biostatistician at Memorial Sloan Kettering. I collaborate closely with clinical researchers and oncologists to design and analyze retrospective studies and clinical trials. Most of this work is in hematologic malignancies, including leukemia, multiple myeloma, and lymphoma, and the treatment areas of blood and marrow transplantation and cellular therapy. I also work on developing new statistical methods, particularly in the area of early-phase clinical trials, and the evaluation of prognostic models.

[1] ODAC recording: [YouTube live video link](#); meeting materials: [April 12, 2024 Meeting of the Oncologic Drugs Advisory Committee Meeting Announcement - 04/12/2024](#) | FDA

Reflections on the ODAC Meeting about MRD as an Endpoint to Support Accelerated Approval

By Gu Mi, Ph.D. †

INTRODUCTION, BACKGROUND, AND CONTEXT FOR THE MEETING

The Oncologic Drugs Advisory Committee (ODAC) of the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) met on April 12, 2024, to discuss the use of **minimal residual disease (MRD)** as an endpoint in multiple myeloma (MM) clinical trials, including considerations regarding timing of assessment, patient populations, and trial design for future studies that intend to use MRD to support accelerated approval (AA) of a new product or a new indication [1,2,3].

Multiple Myeloma (MM) is the second most common hematologic malignancy, making up 17% of such cancers and 1.8% of all new cancer diagnoses annually. Treatment for newly diagnosed patients depends on eligibility for autologous stem cell transplant (ASCT), while relapsed or refractory (RR) cases consider prior therapies and responses. Over the past decade, 15 new drugs and 20+ new indications have been approved, increasing median overall survival (OS) from 3.5 years in the late 1990s to over 10 years, though MM remains incurable with a 5-year survival rate of 59.8%.

While OS is the ultimate endpoint, progression-free survival (PFS) has supported regular approval with an assessment of OS. Traditionally for MM, the accepted endpoint to support accelerated approval has been Overall Response Rate (ORR) which includes patients with partial response (PR) or better as defined by the International Myeloma Working Group criteria (IMWG) supported by duration of response. The FDA Guidance for Industry, *Hematologic Malignancies: Regulatory Considerations for Use of Minimal Residual Disease in Development of Drug and Biological Products for Treatment*, outlines general considerations for developing novel endpoints as surrogates including endpoints based on MRD [4].

Recent improvements in technologies to detect the presence of malignant cells at orders of magnitude below the limit of conventional ORR, has allowed an assessment of MRD in MM. **MRD is a measure of tumor burden assessed in the bone marrow sample.** MRD as a biomarker has multiple regulatory uses including for response assessments and as a prognostic marker.

SUMMARY OF KEY FINDINGS FROM INDUSTRY AND FDA PRESENTATIONS

Based on the briefing document [2], we summarize the results of a meta-analysis conducted by two independent applicants, the University of Miami and i2TEAMM, and the FDA. This analysis used patient-level data from multiple trials to evaluate MRD as a potential regulatory endpoint to support accelerated approval

• Landmark time for MRD assessment

o MM trials typically did not mandate a landmark time for MRD assessment. FDA, in alignment with the two applicants, jointly selected a priori 12 +/- 3 months as “clinically relevant and provided the most complete dataset to analyze MRD negativity” for the primary analyses.

o Both 9-month and 12-month time points may be appropriate for assessment of MRD across different disease settings.

o In **NDTE** (newly diagnosed transplant eligible) setting, MRD negativity at **12-month** may be more appropriate.

o In **RRMM** setting, a **9-month** time point may be more appropriate.

o Durability of MRD negativity may also be needed to support robustness of MRD endpoint if patients are assessed and achieved MRD-CR earlier than 9-12 months. (page 66)

• Individual associations:

o **Bivariate Plackett Copula model** to assess if MRD negativity is a prognostic marker for clinical benefit (PFS).

o Association is measured by odds ratio: odds of having a PFS event at/after 4 years for patients who achieved MRD negativity, over odds of having a PFS event at/after 4 years for patients who did not achieve MRD negativity.

o Odds ratio ≥ 3 is statistically significant (i.e., confidence interval [CI] excludes 1.0).

o **Evidence of prognostic value of MRD is strong.**

o FDA Tables 1 and 2.

• Trial-level associations:

o **Weighted linear regression model; two-stage copula model.**

o Explanatory variable (x): estimated treatment effect on MRD negativity (log odds ratio of MRD negative rate in experimental arm to control arm

o Dependent variable (y): treatment effect on PFS

o Association is measured by R^2 (WLS) and R^2 (Copula). If either value is at least 0.8, with a lower bound of the 95% CI >0.6 and neither estimate is <0.7 , then the MRD surrogate endpoint provides sufficient trial-level surrogacy to replace direct observation of treatment effectiveness on the true clinical outcome (i.e., a “*validated surrogate endpoint*” for regular approval). However, there is no formal FDA guidance specifying these criteria.

o FDA Tables 3 and 4.

o Insufficient evidence to support use of MRD as a “*validated surrogate endpoint*”.

o Sufficient evidence to consider use of **MRD** (tested at a sensitivity of **10⁻⁵** or better) as an endpoint “**reasonably likely**” to predict clinical benefit, alongside confirmatory PFS data in the same trial. (pages 53-54)

• Surrogate Threshold Effect (STE):

o If a surrogate endpoint shows significant association at both individual and trial levels, a subsequent analysis quantifies its predictive ability on the ultimate endpoint, via **surrogate threshold effect (STE)**, defined as the **smallest treatment effect on the surrogate needed to predict a statistically significant treatment effect on the true endpoint.** (page 33)

o STE is computed using a **linear regression between treatment effects: intersecting the 95% prediction limits from the model and the x-axis** (corresponding to no treatment effect for the latter endpoint).

o To observe a statistically significant treatment effect on PFS, the treatment effect on **MRD-CR** would need an **odds ratio between 2.12 and 4.95**, depending on the endpoint and setting. Such treatment effects assume that a future trial has 100% power for PFS. In practice, the treatment effect on MRD-CR may need to be larger (page 58).

o FDA Table 7 provides a hypothetical example of MRD-CR rates needed in the treatment arm based on control rates and selected STE estimates (odds ratios of 2.12 and 4.95).

o The **magnitude** of MRD-CR that would be considered to provide a meaningful advantage over available therapy is **unclear**. In the NDTE + NDTinE (newly diagnosed transplant ineligible) + RR population, the STE for MRD-CR vs. PFS is 3.82. This suggests that in a randomized trial with a 25% MRD-CR rate in the control arm, a 56% rate in the treatment arm is needed to predict a positive effect on PFS.

o FDA Tables 5, 6 and 7 (note: there seems to be an error for the row when MRD-CR rate is 10% in control arm and 25% in treatment arm - the STE odds ratio is not 4.95).

[To be continued on Page 4]

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The Use of Circulating Tumor DNA (ctDNA) in Early-stage Solid Tumor Drug Development

Haijun Ma* and Jonathan Fawcett*

Circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA) is tumor-derived fragmented DNA shed into a patient's bloodstream that is not associated with cells [1]. It offers a non-invasive method for obtaining tumor information, aiding in diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment decisions, without the need for tissue biopsies. Several ctDNA-based companion diagnostic (CDx) assays have been approved by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for targeted therapies, primarily for the treatment of patients with metastatic cancers [2].

ctDNA could also be used in the early stage setting to assist and expedite drug development. FDA in the guidance document "Use of Circulating Tumor DNA for Early-Stage Solid Tumor Drug Development", described a number of potential regulatory and clinical uses of ctDNA.

Potential Uses:

- **Patient Selection:**
 - o ctDNA can be used for patient selection based on molecular alterations.
- **Measure of Response:**
 - o changes in ctDNA levels for signal finding and detection of anti-tumor activities
 - o to assess the effectiveness of therapies and potentially as an early surrogate endpoint in clinical trials.
- **Molecular Residual Disease (MRD):**
 - o The use of ctDNA to detect MRD after definitive therapy (surgery, radiation, or chemoradiation) can help identify patients at high risk of recurrence for patient enrichment.

Challenges:

- **Differences in tumor biology:**
 - o ctDNA quantity can vary among individuals and depends on the type of tumor, location, stage, tumor burden, and response to therapy.
- **Variability in ctDNA assays**
 - o The need for standardization of technologies and validation of ctDNA assays, ensuring consistent sample collection, processing, and analytical validation to support regulatory use.
- **Further data are required for ctDNA as and early endpoint**
 - o Statistical criteria for validating ctDNA as an endpoint reasonably likely to predict long term outcome (DFS/EFS/OS).
 - o Requires correlation with long-term clinical outcomes through meta-analyses.

Circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA) shows great promise for early-stage solid tumor drug development. However, extensive tumour-by-tumour, clinical situation-by-clinical situation validation is required before ctDNA is generally acceptable as a surrogate endpoint for OS and other long-term clinical outcomes. Ongoing clinical trials are exploring ctDNA's role in both early-stage and advanced cancers [4]. Collaborative efforts are essential to generate robust data, standardize ctDNA measurement, and validate ctDNA as an early endpoint. The multiple myeloma community has set a commendable example by validating minimal residual disease (MRD) as a surrogate endpoint likely to predict long-term outcomes for regulatory approval. By following this example, the potential of ctDNA in solid tumors can be fully realized, paving the way for more effective treatments for cancer patients.

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[Continued from Page 3]

Other findings:

- The i2TEAMM study suggests that a 10^{-5} sensitivity level is a better predictor of long-term PFS than 10^{-4} , achieved by sensitive NGF and NGS MRD methodologies. The FDA agrees that a 10^{-5} threshold is appropriate.
- "Delayed transplant" is common after 4-drug combo therapy, making it sensible to combine transplant-eligible and -ineligible NDMM patients.
- Regulatory approval pathways:
 - o MRD can support accelerated approval (AA) in a single trial with sufficient follow-up for long-term outcomes.
 - o Two trials: one for initial AA and another to confirm clinical benefit (confirmatory trial must be underway before receiving AA).
 - o For single-arm trials using MRD-CR, specify a minimum follow-up time to ensure most MRD-CR responses are observed.
- The FDA is agnostic to the technology used (MPFC or NGS), as long as the assay is analytically validated and sensitive to detect a pre-specified MRD negativity threshold.

ODAC voting results

Vote: Does the evidence support the use of MRD as an accelerated approval endpoint in MM clinical trials?

Result: Yes: 12 No: 0 Abstain: 0

CRITICAL QUOTES AND DIFFERENT OPINIONS

"Today's ODAC positive vote – 12-0 in favor – for MRD as an early endpoint for accelerated approval of new multiple myeloma drugs is fantastic news for patients diagnosed with multiple myeloma," said Landgren. "With MRD as a new endpoint, it will give patients access to new therapies much faster! This is exactly what patients need and want." C. Ola Landgren, M.D., Ph.D., is director of Sylvester's Myeloma Research Institute. Landgren led the assessment, called the "EVIDENCE meta-analysis," and presented the findings at the ODAC meeting.

A different perspective on this topic by Vinay Prasad, American hematologist and oncologist: [4-12-24 : My comments at the FDA Advisory meeting on the irresponsible use of MRD for AA \(youtube.com\)](#). Topic #4 (4:48) is about surrogacy built on trial-level evidence rather than individual-level, where the latter is not surrogacy but prognostic factors.

References

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A Summary of the Association Between Pathologic Complete Response (pCR) and Long-term Survival across Multiple Cancer Types

By Natalie Ren ¶, Jean Fan §, Sohail Chaudhry †, Philip He ‡

Neoadjuvant therapies have become a cornerstone in the treatment of patients with various solid tumors, aiming to enhance resectability by downstage tumor size allowing less extensive surgery or achieving local control, identifying sensitivity to systemic treatment, and preventing early metastatic risk. Pathologic complete response (pCR), defined as the absence of residual invasive cancer cells in the resected specimen, has been accepted by FDA recently as a surrogate marker for long-term clinical outcomes such as event-free survival (EFS) to support accelerated approval in neoadjuvant treatment of breast cancer (FDA Guidance 2020). Multiple meta-analyses have been performed to assess the pCR's prognostic surrogacy for long term endpoints such as EFS and OS. Here, we summarize the key data presented in recent publications in the following Table [see next page].

- **Breast cancer:** Achieving pCR is a robust predictor of improved EFS and OS, particularly in subtypes such as TNBC and HER2-positive cancer. Achieving pCR in these settings can influence postoperative treatment decisions, including the need for additional systemic therapy (NCCN guideline).
- **Melanoma:** Achieving pCR following neoadjuvant immunotherapy also experience markedly better survival outcomes by several studies, though data are relatively limited.
- **NSCLC:** Patients achieving pCR after neoadjuvant therapies exhibit significantly better EFS compared to those who do not achieve pCR. pCR is increasingly considered as a clinically important measure of response to neoadjuvant therapies. The trial-level association was found weak between pCR and EFS/OS by Waser et al. (2024).
- **GI cancers:** Several large meta-analyses showed strong associations between pCR and long-term outcomes, while a relatively weaker correlation is observed in KN-585 trial and a meta-analysis in rectal cancer.
- **Ovarian cancer:** pCR was shown associated with improved outcomes in recurrence-free survival (RFS) and OS, though data are relatively limited.
- **Muscle-invasive bladder cancer:** Achieving pCR was found associated with improved RFS and OS, though data are relatively limited.
- **Merkel Cell Carcinoma:** Achieving pCR was found associated with improved RFS, though data are limited.

... the prognostic significance of pCR following neoadjuvant therapies has been increasingly recognized across various tumor types. However, the number of neoadjuvant studies in many tumor types are still limited, making it challenging to conclusively elucidate pCR's correlation with long-term clinical outcomes ...

In general, the prognostic significance of pCR following neoadjuvant therapies has been increasingly recognized across various tumor types. However, the number of neoadjuvant studies in many tumor types are still limited, making it challenging to conclusively elucidate pCR's correlation with long-term clinical outcomes like OS, RFS, and EFS. Continuous assessment of whether pCR is suitable for accelerated approval in tumor types beyond breast cancer should be performed in order to expedite the availability of life-saving therapies.

The strength of the correlation between pCR and EFS varies across different cancers and subgroups. For instance, in breast cancer, pCR is a strong prognostic indicator of EFS in TNBC and HER2-positive subtypes (Spring et al., 2020; Cortazar et al., 2014), but its predictive value is less pronounced in hormone receptor-positive/HER2-negative (HR+/HER2-) subtypes (Gogate et al., 2023). Neoadjuvant immunotherapy demonstrates correlation between pathologic response and long-term survival in various solid tumors based on patient-level analysis (Wei et al. 2024). To draw robust conclusions, multiple statistical methods should be employed when analyzing the relationship between pCR and clinical outcomes. These include patient-level and trial-level assessments using tools such as the Prentice criteria, meta-analytical techniques, the coefficient of determination in weighted linear regression (Sargent et al., 2005), random effect models (Burzykowski et al., 2004), and surrogate threshold effect analyses (Burzykowski & Buyse, 2006).

[to be continued in next page]

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[Continued from previous page.]

Table 1. Summary of findings for pCR's prognosis on EFS and OS across multiple solid tumor types

Study	Findings
Breast Cancer	
Meta-analysis (von Minckwitz et al 2012): n = 6,377 (7 studies)	ypT0 ypN0 is associated with better DFS compared to ypT1s ypN0 (HR = 1.74) and better OS (HR = 1.41); better than ypT0/is ypN+ in DFS (HR = 3.18) and OS (HR = 4.05) or ypT1mic ypN0/+ in DFS (HR = 2.33) and OS (HR = 2.34). pCR was not a predictor for DFS and OS in subgroups of lower proliferation, lobular type, grade 1, ER-positive and PgR-positive status. pCR was prognostic for DFS and OS in ductal and other histologic subtypes, grade 2 or 3 tumors, ER-negative and PgR-negative. pCR had no prognostic impact in luminal-A tumors, while significant prognostic impact in HER2-pos and TNBC. (Saltalamacchia et al., 2023).
Meta-analysis (Berruti et al 2014): n = 14,641 (29 studies)	Regression of either the log(HR) for DFS or the log(HR) for OS on the log(OR) for pCR demonstrated only weak associations (R ² = 0.08; and R ² = 0.09, respectively).
Meta-analysis (Broglio et al 2016) in HER2+: n = 5,768 (36 studies)	EFS for pCR vs non-pCR was significant (HR = .37). Hormone receptor-negative (HR = 0.29) than hormone receptor-positive (HR = .52).
Meta-analysis (Cortazar et al., 2014): n = 11,955 (12 studies)	Overall: EFS HR 0.48 (95% CI 0.43–0.54), OS HR 0.36. HR-pos HER2-: EFS HR 0.49 and OS HR 0.43. HER2-pos: EFS HR 0.39 and OS HR 0.34. HR-neg: EFS HR 0.25, OS HR 0.19. TNBC: EFS HR 0.24. R ² = 0.03 and 0.24 for EFS and OS.
Meta-analysis (Spring et al., 2020): n = 27,895 (52 studies)	pCR is associated with improved EFS in TNBC, HER2-pos, and HR-pos. The 5-year EFS rates were 88% vs 67% for those with vs without pCR respectively. Patients with a pCR after NAT had significantly better EFS (HR = 0.31), particularly for TNBC (HR = 0.18) and HER2-pos (HR = 0.32) disease. Similarly, pCR after NAT was also associated with improved survival (HR = 0.22).
Meta-analysis (Huang et al 2020) in TNBC: n = 4,330 (25 studies)	pCR was associated with improved EFS [HR = .24] and OS [HR = .19]. The 5-year EFS was 86% vs 50% for pCR vs no pCR. The 5-year OS was 92% vs 58% for pCR vs no pCR.
Meta-analysis (Davey et al., 2022) in HER2+: n = 25,150 (78 studies)	HER2-pos: pCR predicted better EFS (HR 0.67; 41 studies), RFS (HR 0.69; 18 studies) and OS (HR 0.63; 29 studies).
NSCLC	
Meta-analysis (Rosner et al., 2022): n = 7,011 (28 studies)	pCR rate was associated with significant improvements in OS (HR: 0.50) and EFS (HR: 0.46).
Meta-analysis (Banna et al., 2024): n = 3,387 (8 studies)	Neoadjuvant chemo-immunotherapy was associated with improved 2-year EFS (HR 0.57) and increased pCR rate (RR 5.58). No reports were provided about the comparison of EFS for pCR vs non-pCR patients.
Meta-analysis (Hines et al. 2024): n = 2,385 (7 studies)	At the patient level, the R ² of pCR with 2-year EFS was 0.82. The odds ratio of 2-year EFS rates by response status was 0.12 (0.07–0.19). At the trial level, the R ² for the association of odds ratio of response and HR of EFS was 0.58.
Meta-analysis (Waser et al 2024) resectable NSCLC: n = 6,530 (20 studies)	OS HR = 0.49 for pCR vs no pCR (20 studies, n = 6,530); and similarly for MPR vs no MPR (HR = 0.36). EFS by pCR status, the HR was 0.49 (11 studies n=2,156). Trial-level analyses did not show a strong correlation between pCR and OS (R ² = 0.045) or EFS (R ² = 0.319).
Melanoma	
OpACIN-neo trial (Verlusch 2023): n = 86	The 3-year recurrence-free survival (RFS) for pCR vs non-pCR: 95% vs 37% (P < 0.001).
Study NCT024434354 (Sharon et al., 2023): n = 30	Five-year follow-up after 1 neoadjuvant pembrolizumab followed by 1 year of adjuvant pembrolizumab: 0 death for MPR or pCR vs 72.8% others.
Study NCT04949113 (Blank et al., 2024): n = 423	pCR associated with 5-year EFS of 83% vs. 53% for non-pCR; 5-year OS of 89% vs. 64% for non-pCR.

Study	Findings
GI Cancers	
Gastroesophageal: MAGIC trial (Cunningham et al., 2006): n = 503	pCR, evaluated according to the TRG system, was significantly correlated with OS in patients who received chemotherapy (TRG 3-5: HR 1.94; P = .021). 5-year OS rate: 58.8% vs 28.9% for those with TRG 1-2 vs TRG 3-5.
Rectal: Meta-analysis (Petrelli et al. 2017): n = 10,050 (22 studies).	Patient level: change of pCR is correlated weakly with change of OS 5-year rate (R ² = 0.28). 3-year DFS rate and OS was similarly (R ² =0.37). Trial level: R ² = 0.41 and 0.04 respectively.
Esophageal: Retrospective study (Murphy et al 2017): n = 911	pCR was associated with better OS (median 71.28 vs 35.87 mo) and higher 5-year OS rate 52% vs 41% compared to non-pCR; was also associated with better RFS (median 70.75 vs 26.07 mo).
Esophagus: Retrospective study (Lin et al. 2018): n = 68	pCR is associated with higher 2-year OS rate 81.3% vs 58.3% (P = 0.025).
Esophageal: Retrospective study (Soro et al 2018): n = 56	pCR is associated with higher 5-year OS rate (47.2% vs 27.3%) and 5-year DFS rate (48% vs 21%); better local recurrence (median 3.8 vs 1.8 years) while similarly distant metastasis (1.2 vs 1.1 years).
Meta-analysis (Wan et al 2019): n = 6,780 (21 studies)	5 GI cancers are included: esophageal cancer, esophagogastric junction AC, gastric AC, rectal cancer and pancreatic cancer. OS (HR = .50, P < .001) and DFS (HR = .49, P < .001) for pCR vs non-pCR. In EGJAC/GAC, the correlation of pCR with OS was significant (HR = .38, p: .02).
Gastric: Meta-analysis (Li et al. 2018): n = 1,143 (7 studies)	RR of pCR vs non-pCR is 0.5 (p<0.0001), 0.34 (p<0.0001), and 0.44 (p<0.0001) for 1, 3, 5-year-OS, respectively. RR for 3-year DFS was 0.43 (p = 0.002).
Gastric: KEYNOTE-585 (Shitara et al. 2024): n = 804	pCR: 12.9% vs 2.0% for pembrolizumab + chemo vs chemo (p<0.00001); median EFS 44.4 vs 25.3 mo; HR 0.81 and did not meet the threshold for statistical significance. Median OS was 60.7 vs 58.0 mo (HR 0.90).
Rectal: RAPIDO trial (Saltalamacchia et al., 2023): n = 912	pCR: 28% in the experimental group vs 14% in the SOC (OR 2.37; P < .001), while the disease-related treatment failure was 23.7% vs 30.4% (HR = .75; P = .019)
Rectal: Meta-analysis (Petrelli et al., 2017): n = 10,050 (22 studies)	The individual level analysis showed that the pCR% and 3-year DFS were poorly correlated with 5-year OS (R=0.52, 0.60 respectively). The trial-level analysis is consistent with the findings (ΔpCR% and Δ3yDFS) are not strong surrogates for treatment effects on 5-year OS % (R=0.2, 0.64 respectively).
Ovarian Cancer	
Retrospective study (LaFargue et al. 2022): n = 472	Median RFS of 24.3 months for pCR patients versus 11.9 months for non-pCR patients and a median OS of 54.5 months versus 39.9 months, respectively
Retrospective study (Le et al 2007): n = 62	Predictors for prolonged PFS: younger age, optimal tumour residual status, and higher composite pathologic tumour response score (HR 0.848), where the last one is also associated to time to disease related death (HR 0.695).
Retrospective study (Petrillo et al 2014a): n = 322	Median PFS was 36 mo in cPR, 16 in microPR, and 13 in macroPR (P = .001). Median OS was 72 mo in cPR, 38 in microPR, and 29 in macroPR (P = .018).
Bladder Cancer	
MIBC: (Grossman et al 2003): n = 307	In M-VAC and cystectomy group, median OS is NR vs 3.8 years for pT0 vs non-PT0; and in cystectomy group, median OS is 11.3 vs 2.4 years for pT0 vs non-PT0.
Meta-analysis (Petrelli et al. 2014b): n = 886 (13 studies)	Patients who achieved pCR in the primary tumour and the lymph nodes presented an RR for OS of 0.45 (p<0.00001). RR for RFS was 0.19 (p<0.00001).
Merkel Cell Carcinoma	
CheckMate 358 trial (Topalian et al 2020) n=36	High pCR (47.2%) was observed; no patient with a pCR experienced tumor relapse, with 19.3 months of median follow-up postoperatively. RFS at 12 months (pCR vs non-pCR): 100% vs 59.6%, at 24 months: 88.9% versus 52.2%; and RFS HR: 0.12.

Disclaimer: Please note the views and opinions expressed are those of the authors and are not intended to reflect the views and/or opinions of their employer(s).

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Dahshu IDSWG Oncology Working Group Highlights

Two manuscripts by the seamless designs team were published:

- "A Systematic Review of Adaptive Seamless Clinical Trials for Late-Phase Oncology Development", Ther Innov Regul Sci 58, 917-929 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43441-024-00670-1>
- "Use of seamless study designs in Oncology Clinical Development – A survey conducted by IDSWG oncology sub-team" Ther Innov Regul Sci. 2024 Sep;58(5):978-986. doi: 10.1007/s43441-024-00676-9. Epub 2024 Jun 22. PMID: 38909174.

One session was organized at JSM

- Examples and Perspectives Using Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence in Drug Development

WG F2F meeting and dinner at Portland

Upcoming Conferences

- [ASA BIOP Regulatory-Industry Statistics Workshop](#), Sept. 25-27, 2024, Rockville, Maryland
- [Bernoulli-IMS 11th World Congress in Probability and Statistics](#), August 12-16, 2024, Bochum, Germany
- [Royal Statistical Society \(RSS\) 2024 International Conference](#), September 02 – 05, 2024, Brighton, UK
- [International Conference on Advances in Interdisciplinary Statistics and Combinatorics \(AISC-2024\)](#), October 11-13, 2024, Greensboro, NC, USA
- [R/Pharma Summit and Workshop](#), Aug 11-12, 2024, Seattle, WA, USA
- [R/Pharma 2024 virtual conference](#), Oct 29-31 with workshops the week before.
- [Women in Statistics and Data Science \(WSDS\) Conference](#), October 16 – 18, 2024, Reston, VA, USA
- [Bayesian Biostatistics Conference Bayes 2024](#), October 23 – 25, 2024, Rockville, MA, USA
- [The Bay Area Biotech-Pharma Statistics Workshop \(BBSW\) 2024](#), OCT 24-25, 2024, FOSTER CITY, CA, USA
- [BASS XXXI](#), 31ST ANNUAL BIOPHARMACEUTICAL APPLIED STATISTICS SYMPOSIUM, November 4-6, 2024, Savannah, GA.

FDA Oncologic Drugs Advisory Committee (ODAC) Q2' 2024

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Date	ODAC Agenda	Indication	Vote Result	YouTube Link
4/12/2024	Use of minimal residual disease (MRD) as an endpoint in multiple myeloma clinical trials, including considerations regarding timing of assessment, patient populations, and trial design for future studies that intend to use MRD to support accelerated approval of a new product or a new indication.	Multiple myeloma	12:0 to support the use of MRD as an accelerated approval endpoint in multiple myeloma clinical trials	YouTube
5/22/2024	Perspectives relating to implementation of 2017 FDARA legislation and its impact on pediatric cancer drug development to date. For original applications submitted on or after August 18, 2020, pediatric investigations of certain targeted cancer drugs with new active ingredients will be based on their molecular mechanism of action rather than clinical indications.	NA	Vote not requested	YouTube
6/25/2024	Discuss the use of IMFINZI in combination with platinum-containing chemotherapy as neoadjuvant treatment, followed by IMFINZI as monotherapy after surgery, for the treatment of adult patients with resectable (tumors ≥ 4 cm and/or node positive) non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) and no known epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) mutations or anaplastic lymphoma kinase (ALK) rearrangements.	Resectable non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC)	11:0 to agree that FDA should require that new trial design proposals for perioperative regimens for resectable NSCLC include an adequate trial assessment of the contribution of each treatment phase	YouTube

Prepared by Fengyu Zhao, FDA CDER

FDA Oncology Approvals in Q2 2024

Click the links to access to the FDA's official review materials.

Date	Generic Name	Indication
4/5/2024	fam-trastuzumab deruxtecan-nxki	adult patients with unresectable or metastatic HER2-positive (IHC3+) solid tumors who have received prior systemic treatment and have no satisfactory alternative treatment options
4/18/2024	alectinib	adjuvant treatment following tumor resection in patients with anaplastic lymphoma kinase (ALK)-positive non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC)
4/22/2024	nogapendekin alfa inbakicept-pmIn	adult patients with BCG-unresponsive non-muscle invasive bladder cancer (NMIBC) with carcinoma in situ (CIS) with or without papillary tumors
4/23/2024	lutetium Lu 177 dotatate	pediatric patients 12 years and older with somatostatin receptor (SSTR)-positive gastroenteropancreatic neuroendocrine tumors (GEP-NETs)
4/23/2024	tovorafenib	patients 6 months of age and older with relapsed or refractory pediatric low-grade glioma (LGG) harboring a BRAF fusion or rearrangement, or BRAF V600 mutation
4/29/2024	tisotumab vedotin-tftv	recurrent or metastatic cervical cancer with disease progression on or after chemotherapy
5/15/2024	lisocabtagene maraleuceL	adults with relapsed or refractory follicular lymphoma (FL) who have received two or more prior lines of systemic therapy
5/16/2024	tarlatamab-dlle	extensive stage small cell lung cancer (ES-SCLC) with disease progression on or after platinum-based chemotherapy
5/29/2024	selpercatinib	advanced or metastatic medullary thyroid cancer (MTC) with a RET mutation; advanced or metastatic thyroid cancer with a RET gene fusion; locally advanced or metastatic solid tumors with a RET gene fusion
5/30/2024	lisocabtagene maraleuceL	adult patients with relapsed or refractory mantle cell lymphoma (MCL) who have received at least two prior lines of systemic therapy
6/6/2024	imetelstat	adults with low- to intermediate-1 risk myelodysplastic syndromes (MDS) with transfusion-dependent anemia requiring four or more red blood cell units over 8 weeks
6/12/2024	selpercatinib	adult and pediatric patients 2 years of age and older with advanced or metastatic RET fusion-positive thyroid cancer who require systemic therapy and who are radioactive iodine-refractory
6/13/2024	repotrectinib	adult and pediatric patients 12 years and older with solid tumors that have a neurotrophic tyrosine receptor kinase (NTRK) gene fusion
6/14/2024	durvalumab	carboplatin plus paclitaxel followed by single-agent durvalumab for adult patients with primary advanced or recurrent endometrial cancer that is mismatch repair deficient (dMMR)
6/14/2024	blinatumomab	adult and pediatric patients one month and older with CD19-positive Philadelphia chromosome-negative B-cell precursor acute lymphoblastic leukemia (Ph-negative BCP ALL) in the consolidation phase of multiphase chemotherapy
6/17/2024	pembrolizumab	carboplatin and paclitaxel, followed by single-agent pembrolizumab, for adult patients with primary advanced or recurrent endometrial carcinoma
6/21/2024	adagrasib plus cetuximab	adults with KRAS G12C-mutated locally advanced or metastatic colorectal cancer (CRC)
6/26/2024	epcoritamab-byssp	adult patients with relapsed or refractory follicular lymphoma (FL) after two or more lines of systemic therapy

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Surrogate and Intermediate Endpoints

By Revathi Ananthkrishnan *, Haijun Ma ^, Philip He †

In clinical trials, a **surrogate endpoint** is an indicator used in place of the actual clinical outcomes of interest to tell if a treatment works.

Surrogate endpoints include a shrinking tumor or lower biomarker levels[1]. They may be used instead of stronger indicators, such as longer survival, so that the results of the trial can be measured sooner. The use of surrogate endpoints in clinical trials may allow earlier approval of new drugs to treat serious or life-threatening diseases, such as cancer.

In the FDA guidance [2], *Hematologic Malignancies: Regulatory Considerations for Use of Minimal Residual Disease in Development of Drug and Biological Products for Treatment Guidance for Industry* in 2020, it explained that the strength of evidence required for a surrogate endpoint is: (A). Based on the biological plausibility of the relationship (B). Demonstration of the prognostic value of the surrogate endpoint for the clinical outcome, and (C). Evidence from clinical trials that treatment effects on the surrogate endpoint correspond to effects on the long-term clinical outcome. The surrogate endpoints used for cancer drug approvals by FDA are listed in Table 1 with contents as of February 28, 2022 [3].

Validation of a surrogate endpoint

Figure 1 below illustrates the validation of a surrogate endpoint. When the intervention works exclusively through the causal pathway relating the surrogate to the true clinical outcome, this offers the greatest chance for the surrogate to be valid. Buyse et al., *Nat Rev Clin Oncol* 2010; 7:309-317 [4] discussed the Individual versus Trial level surrogacy.

Individual-level “surrogacy”:

- A variable that is a correlate or prognostic for the true endpoint within the context of the specified treatment and patient subpopulation.
- May be demonstrated in the context of a single clinical trial.

Trial-level “surrogacy”

- A variable or endpoint that can replace the true clinical trial endpoint.
- Requires meta-analyses of clinical trials to show that the conclusion about the treatment effect based on the surrogate reliably agrees with the conclusion obtained using the true endpoint.
- Evidence needed to use a surrogate as a new endpoint in a new trial.

Figure 1. Validation of a surrogate endpoint [5]

Four types of endpoints

The term 'surrogate endpoint' has been applied with differing degrees of rigor. In the context of a recent ODAC meeting discussing MRD as an approval endpoint, Gormley (2024) [6] provided further clarification on its terminology (Figure 2):

1. Clinical benefit endpoints: which could be summarized as a measure of how a patient feels, functions, or survives but really captures a clinically relevant and important treatment benefit.
2. Surrogate endpoints that predict clinical benefit but is not a direct measure of clinical benefit. In this instance the endpoint has been fully clinically validated to predict clinical benefits.
3. Surrogate endpoints that are reasonably likely to predict clinical benefit. It may be a predictor of clinical benefit, but lacks robust validation data to confirm that it is a surrogate.
4. Intermediate endpoints, which are measurements of therapeutic effects that can be measured earlier than morbidity or mortality and are deemed reasonably likely to predict clinical benefit.

Figure 2. Illustration of 4 types of endpoints according to Gormley (2024) [6].

The first two types of endpoints are used to support regular approvals while the last two are used to support accelerated approvals. Most accelerated approvals in oncology are based on intermediate clinical endpoints. It is rare that there are true surrogates in oncology [6]. In order for a biomarker to be a true surrogate for a long-term outcome of interest, it should be in the causal pathway between treatment of the disease and a true clinical endpoint of interest.

An **intermediate clinical endpoint** is a measure of a therapeutic effect that is considered reasonably likely to predict the clinical benefit of a drug, such as an effect on irreversible morbidity and mortality (IMM) [7]. For instance, exercise tolerance is an intermediate endpoint predictive of heart failure [8]. Not all intermediate endpoints can be a surrogate endpoint. Even if intermediate end points such as ORR and PFS are not established as valid surrogate end points, they can be useful as supportive end points in phase 3 trials or as primary end points in proof-of-concept trials insofar as they provide substantive evidence about biological effects [9]. FDA can accept a proposed surrogate or intermediate endpoint based on support from “adequate and well controlled” studies as required by the Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic (FD&C) Act [8].

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Table 2. Surrogate Endpoints That Were the Basis of FDA Drug Approval or Licensure – Oncology (as of Feb 28, 2022)

	Patient Population	Surrogate endpoint	Appropriate for Approval
HM	Patients with acute lymphoblastic leukemia; B-cell lymphoma; Pediatric. Age: 1 to 21 years	Durable ORR	AA / TA §
HM	Patients with acute lymphoblastic leukemia; Pediatric. Age: 1 to 21 years	EFS	AA / TA §
HM	Patients with chronic myeloid leukemia; Pediatric. Age: 3 to 20 years	Major hematologic and cytogenetic response	AA / TA §
HM	Patients with Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia; Pediatric. Age: All pediatric age groups	Serum Asparaginase	TA
HM	Patients with Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia	Serum asparaginase	TA
HM	Patients with chronic myeloid leukemia	Major hematologic response	AA / TA §
HM	Patients with acute myeloid leukemia and acute lymphoblastic leukemia	Durable complete remission rate	AA / TA §
HM	Patients with acute lymphoblastic leukemia; myelodysplastic/myeloproliferative diseases; chronic myeloid leukemia	Major hematologic response and cytogenetic response	AA / TA §
HM	Patients with B-cell precursor acute lymphoblastic leukemia in first or second complete remission	MRD response rate	AA
HM	Chronic myelogenous leukemia	Durable major molecular response	TA
HM	Patients with diffuse large B-cell lymphoma	EFS#	TA
HM	Diffuse large B-Cell lymphoma; hairy cell leukemia; follicular lymphoma	Durable CR	AA / TA §
HM	Patients with multiple myeloma; mantle cell lymphoma; classical Hodgkin lymphoma; follicular lymphoma; B-cell lymphoma; systemic anaplastic large cell lymphoma; chronic myeloid leukemia; chronic lymphocytic leukemia; cutaneous T cell lymphoma; all other non-Hodgkin lymphoma; chronic lymphocytic leukemia; mycosis fungoides	PFS	TA
HM	Patients with T-cell lymphoma; B-cell lymphoma; mantle cell lymphoma; classical Hodgkin lymphoma; anaplastic large cell lymphoma and mycosis fungoides; non-Hodgkin lymphoma; multiple myeloma; chronic myeloid leukemia; acute lymphoblastic leukemia; chronic lymphocytic leukemia; acute myeloid leukemia; small lymphocytic lymphoma; Waldenström's macroglobulinemia; marginal zone lymphoma; follicular	Durable ORR	AA / TA §
ST	Patients with tuberous sclerosis complex with subependymal giant cell astrocytoma; merkel cell carcinoma; neurotrophic receptor tyrosine kinase (NTRK) gene fusion without a known acquired resistance mutation; thyroid cancer; tumor mutational burden high solid tumors; neuroblastoma; Pediatric. Age: 28 days and older	Durable ORR	AA
ST	Patients with metastatic melanoma; Pediatric. Age: 12 years and older	PFS	AA
ST	Patients with breast cancer	pCR	AA
ST	Patients with nonmetastatic castrate-resistant prostate cancer	MFS	AA / TA §
ST	Patients with advanced prostate cancer	Plasma testosterone levels	TA
ST	Patients with breast cancer; ovarian cancer; renal cell carcinoma; pancreatic neuroendocrine cancer; colorectal cancer; head and neck cancer; non-small cell lung cancer; melanoma; tuberous sclerosis complex-associated SEGA and renal angiomyolipoma; merkel cell carcinoma; unresectable or metastatic cutaneous basal cell carcinoma; urothelial carcinoma; cervical cancer; endometrial cancer; hepatocellular carcinoma; fallopian tube cancer; microsatellite instability-high cancer; gastric cancer; gastroesophageal junction cancer; thyroid cancer; astrocytoma; Kaposi's sarcoma; unresectable or metastatic cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma; neurotrophic receptor tyrosine kinase (NTRK) gene fusion without a known acquired resistance mutation; prostate cancer; esophageal cancer; tumor mutational burden high solid tumors; cholangiocarcinoma; bladder cancer; neuroblastoma; mismatch repair deficient solid tumors	Durable ORR	AA / TA §
ST	Patients with breast cancer; renal cell carcinoma; pancreatic neuroendocrine tumor; soft tissue sarcoma; ovarian, fallopian tube, or primary peritoneal cancer; prostate cancer; thyroid cancer; colorectal cancer; non-small cell lung cancer; head and neck cancer; tuberous sclerosis complex; merkel cell carcinoma; basal cell carcinoma; urothelial carcinoma; cervical cancer; endometrial cancer; hepatocellular carcinoma; fallopian tube cancer; melanoma; astrocytoma; gastrointestinal stromal tumors	PFS	AA / TA §
ST	Patients receiving adjuvant therapy following complete surgical resection of colon cancer; colorectal cancer; melanoma; renal cell cancer; gastrointestinal stromal tumor; breast cancer and adjuvant therapy for-stage III non-small cell lung cancer	DFS	AA / TA §
ST	Patients with breast cancer; neuroblastoma	EFS#	AA / TA §

HM: Hematological Malignancies; ST: Solid Tumors. ORR: objective overall response rate; EFS: Event-free Survival; MFS: Metastasis-free survival; PFS: Progression-free survival; pCR: Pathological complete response; MRD: Minimal residual disease; CR: complete response rate; DFS: Disease-free survival; AA: Accelerated Approval; TA: Traditional Approval. § Pediatric patient. # Endpoints based on changes in tumor burden may be used for both traditional and accelerated approval depending on context of use, including factors such as disease, effect size, effect duration, residual uncertainty and benefits of other available therapy. # The agency anticipates that this surrogate endpoint could be appropriate for use as a primary efficacy clinical trial endpoint for drug or biologic approval, although it has not yet been used to support an approved NDA or BLA. Source: FDA 2022. Table of Surrogate Endpoints That Were the Basis of Drug Approval or Licensure. <https://www.fda.gov/drugs/development-resources/table-surrogate-endpoints-were-basis-drug-approval-or-licensure>

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